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ASSESSING THE SOURCES AND QUALITY OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH USING THE SOLOW MODEL

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Abstract. This article analyzes the structural and factor decomposition of economic growth across the districts of Surxondaryo region using the Solow–Swan dynamic growth model and the Cobb–Douglas production function. The study evaluates the sources of regional economic growth, resource quality, sustainability, and diversification level, and develops a single integrated index. The results indicate that economic growth in most districts of the region is mainly driven by capital and labor inputs, reflecting an extensive growth pattern. Intensive, or technology-driven, growth trends were identified only in the city of Termez and Boysun district. The article concludes with practical recommendations aimed at increasing labor productivity and ensuring sustainable economic growth in the regions.

Keywords: economic growth, Solow–Swan model, Cobb–Douglas model, decomposition, integrated index, intensive growth, extensive growth, resource quality, Surxondaryo region.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Surxondaryo viloyati tumanlari kesimida iqtisodiy o‘shishning tarkibiy va omilli dekompozitsiyasi Solow–Swan dinamik o‘shish modeli hamda Cobb–Douglas ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi asosida tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda hududiy iqtisodiy o‘shish manbalari, resurslar sifati, barqarorlik darajasi va diversifikatsiya holati baholanib, yagona integrallashgan indeks shakllantirilgan. Tahlil natijalari viloyatning aksariyat tumanlarida iqtisodiy o‘shish asosan kapital va mehnat omillari hisobiga shakllanayotganini, ya’ni ekstensiv xususiyatga ega ekanini ko‘rsatdi. Intensiv, ya’ni texnologik o‘shish tendensiyalari faqat Termiz shahri va Boysun tumanida kuzatildi. Maqola yakunida hududlarda mehnat unumdorligini oshirish hamda barqaror iqtisodiy o‘shishni ta’minlashga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: iqtisodiy o‘shish, Solow–Swan modeli, Cobb–Douglas modeli, dekompozitsiya, integrallashgan indeks, intensiv o‘shish, ekstensiv o‘shish, resurslar sifati, Surxondaryo viloyati.

Аннотация. В данной статье проведён структурный и факторный декомпозиционный анализ экономического роста по районам Сурхандарьинской области на основе динамической модели экономического роста Солоу–Свона и производственной функции Кобба–Дугласа. В исследовании оценены источники регионального экономического роста, качество ресурсов, уровень устойчивости и степень диверсификации, а также сформирован единый интегральный индекс. Результаты анализа показывают, что в большинстве районов области экономический рост в основном обеспечивается за счёт факторов капитала и труда, что свидетельствует о его экстенсивном характере. Интенсивные, то есть технологически обусловленные, тенденции роста выявлены только в городе Термезе и Байсунском районе. В заключительной части статьи разработаны практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение производительности труда и обеспечение устойчивого экономического роста в регионах.

Ключевые слова: экономический рост, модель Солоу–Свона, модель Кобба–Дугласа, декомпозиция, интегральный индекс, интенсивный рост, экстенсивный рост, качество ресурсов, Сурхандарьинская область.

INTRODUCTION

According to the Solow model [5], economic growth is primarily determined by capital accumulation, labor resources, and technological progress. This model provides an analytical framework for examining regional growth patterns by decomposing the main factors that contribute to economic expansion.

At the same time, it is important to determine not only the structure of economic growth but also its nature, namely whether it is intensive or extensive. This distinction makes it possible to identify whether regional economic expansion is driven mainly by the accumulation of production factors or by improvements in technological efficiency.

Furthermore, factor decomposition allows researchers to determine which regions are growing more rapidly and which are able to generate higher output with relatively fewer resources. In this context, technological progress serves as one of the key indicators of the quality of economic growth. Growth based on innovation, productivity, and efficient resource use reflects a higher level of economic sustainability.

The above considerations highlight the importance of assessing the sources, efficiency, and quality of economic growth. For example, if decomposition results show that regional growth is largely dependent on capital accumulation, this indicates the need to strengthen human capital development, workforce upskilling, and education.

Consequently, the decomposition of regional economic growth provides important insights into which regions are more efficient, which regions are expanding more rapidly, what factors drive this expansion, and whether the growth process is qualitative and sustainable. Since such an assessment involves several analytical stages, it requires a well-structured methodological approach for accurate and comprehensive implementation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The quality of economic growth has been widely examined by various economists from both theoretical and methodological perspectives. In particular, M.A. Mamatov [7], M.V. Gelin [4], and B.D. Babaev et al. [3] conducted theoretical analyses of economic growth and its key determinants. In addition, M.N. Teplov [8] and G.T. Shkiperova [9] focused on the quantitative assessment of regional economic growth, paying particular attention to measurement approaches and evaluation criteria.

The analytical aspects of this process are reflected in the studies of A.N. Mohammad [2], while the application of economic modeling methods is discussed in the scholarly works of M. Achelashvili et al. [1]. Overall, the reviewed literature indicates that assessing the quality of economic growth requires an integrated approach that combines theoretical foundations, quantitative evaluation, and economic modeling.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To assess economic growth, it is first necessary to decompose it into its main contributing factors. In this study, economic growth ((g_Y)) is divided into capital growth ((g_K)), labor growth ((g_L)), and technological efficiency growth ((g_A)). For this purpose, the Solow–Swan model is applied.

The Solow–Swan dynamic growth model is based on the Cobb–Douglas production function and is expressed as follows [6]:

$$g_Y = g_A + \alpha \cdot g_K + \beta \cdot g_L \quad (1)$$

Based on the results of this decomposition, the indicators presented in Table 1 are evaluated.

Table 1
Indicators for Assessing Economic Growth

Indicator	Formula	Description
Resource Quality of Growth	$QI_i = \frac{g_A}{g_Y}$	This indicator measures the quality of economic growth. If the ratio is close to 1, it indicates that growth is mainly driven by technological efficiency. Otherwise, it suggests that growth is primarily based on the accumulation of production resources.
Structural Shares	The share of districts in the volume of the regional gross domestic product (GRP): $k_i = \frac{YaHM_i}{YaHM}$ Capital and labor efficiency: $d_i = \alpha_i AP_{K_i} + \beta_i AP_{L_i}$ where, AP_{K_i} – capital productivity of district, AP_{L_i} – labour productivity of district. General formula: $Sch_i = k_i \cdot d_i$	The structural share index ((Sch_i)) reflects the contribution of each district to overall regional efficiency through the distribution and use of resources across districts.
Social Index of Growth Quality	$SQ_i = \bar{g}_Y \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha YaHM_i}{\alpha YaHM} \right)$ where, $\alpha YaHM_i$ – per capita gross regional product of the district i ; $\alpha YaHM$ – average per capita gross regional product by districts	This indicator shows the social dimension of growth quality. If a district demonstrates high economic growth but its per capita output remains below the regional average, the social contribution of such growth to public welfare is relatively limited.

Sustainability Coefficient of Growth	$SI_i = 1 - \overline{\sigma_{gY_i}^2}$ where, $\sigma_{gY_i}^2$ - Growth variance	Growth stability is assessed using variance. In this case, the normalized variance, scaled between 0 and 1, is subtracted from 1. A higher value of the coefficient indicates more sustainable and stable growth.
Degree of Economic Growth Diversification	$DI_i = 1 - \overline{HHI_i}$ where, HHI_i - concentration index	The diversification coefficient is calculated by normalizing the sectoral concentration index and subtracting it from 1. A higher value indicates a more diversified structure of economic growth.

Aggregating all the indicators evaluated above by normalizing them within the range from 0 to 1 using the Min-Max method and combining them into a single integrated index based on statistically determined weights provides a comprehensive solution to this methodological issue:

$$GQI_i = \omega_1 QI_i + \omega_2 SSh_i + \omega_3 SQ_i + \omega_4 SI_i + \omega_5 DI_i \quad (2)$$

where, ω_i – denotes the weights.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the production model, which decomposes the gross regional product by districts into capital, labor, and technological progress components, are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Production Model Results by Districts

No.	Regions	Cobb-Douglas model	Elasticity of investment	Elasticity of employment
1	Surkhandarya		0,638	0,362
2	Termez district		0,635	0,365
3	Oltinsoy		0,538	0,462
4	Angor		0,597	0,403
5	Boysun		0,417	0,583
6	Muzrabot		0,661	0,339
7	Denov		0,546	0,454
8	Jarkurgan		0,627	0,373
9	Qumkurgan		0,771	0,229
10	Qiziriq		0,611	0,389
11	Sariosiyo		0,671	0,329
12	Termez region		0,686	0,314
13	Uzun		0,52	0,48
14	Sherobod		0,498	0,502
15	Shurchi		0,596	0,404

According to the table, the shares of capital and labor in Oltinsoy, Uzun, and Sherobod districts are almost equal. This indicates that these districts have a relatively balanced growth structure, with economic growth depending on both factors to a similar extent. In Boysun district, economic growth is primarily driven by the labor factor, whereas in the remaining districts, capital plays a dominant role. This suggests that economic growth in most districts is largely extensive in nature.

The regional average elasticity of fixed capital investment is 0.596, which is considerably higher than the elasticity of employment. The highest capital elasticity is observed in Qumqo'rg'on District (0.771), Termiz District (0.686), and Sariosiyo District (0.671). At the same time, relatively high labor elasticity is recorded in Boysun District (0.583) and Sherobod District (0.502).

Based on the analysis results, it can be concluded that districts with a large labor resource base and high capital elasticity have significant potential to further increase labor productivity through more efficient use of

investment and technological modernization.

The decomposition of economic growth by districts was carried out using the Solow–Swan model, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Decomposition of Economic Growth and the Contributions of Capital and Labor

Regions	Average growth	Contribution of capital	Contribution of labor ()	
Termez district	0,146	0,066	0,001	0,080
Oltinsoy	0,113	0,090	0,005	0,018
Angor	0,151	0,161	0,005	-0,015
Boysun	0,091	-0,005	-0,008	0,104
Muzrabot	0,121	0,155	-0,004	-0,030
Denov	0,112	0,077	0,007	0,028
Jarkurgan	0,076	0,133	0,010	-0,067
Qumkurgan	0,081	0,192	0,005	-0,117
Qiziriq	0,112	0,211	0,018	-0,117
Sariosiyo	0,087	0,158	0,001	-0,072
Termez	0,096	0,162	-0,023	-0,042
Uzun	0,131	0,157	0,003	-0,029
Sherobod	0,098	0,056	-0,002	0,044
Shurchi	0,120	0,180	0,000	-0,060

The results presented in Table 3 further confirm the analysis discussed above. The data show that fixed capital investment plays a dominant role in economic growth. In some cases, the contribution of capital exceeds the overall rate of economic growth. This indicates that rapid capital accumulation has compensated for the relatively limited contributions of labor and technological factors. For example, in Qiziriq and Qumqo'rg'on districts, the high contribution of capital offset the lower efficiency of other production factors. In Boysun district, by contrast, growth was mainly driven by technological improvement and more efficient resource use, which compensated for the relatively low contributions of both capital and labor.

Overall, the regional economy remains largely dependent on production resources, while technological progress has considerable potential for further development. Moreover, the relatively low contribution of the labor factor indicates that employment growth has not yet translated into a sufficiently strong increase in output, which highlights the importance of improving labor productivity and human capital quality.

Quality of Growth (QI). This indicator was calculated as the ratio of the technological factor ((g_A)), identified through decomposition, to the overall economic growth rate ((g_V)). In essence, the QI index represents the ratio (g_A/g_V) . If this ratio exceeds 0.5, it indicates that more than half of economic growth is generated by technological progress. This pattern is observed in Boysun district and Termez district, suggesting the presence of intensive growth in these areas. In contrast, negative values of the indicator show that economic growth is mainly dependent on resource accumulation. In Qumqo'rg'on (-1.43) and Qiziriq (-1.05) , economic growth is predominantly extensive in nature.

In turn, the share of extensive growth can be expressed as the ratio of the combined growth rates of capital and labor to the overall growth rate. The calculations show that this indicator is particularly high in Qumqo'rg'on (2.43) , Qiziriq (2.04) , and Jarqo'rg'on (1.88) . In these districts, it is advisable to strengthen measures aimed at transitioning toward intensive growth, improving the quality of economic growth, and increasing technological efficiency.

Structural Shares. The structural share index (SCh) reflects the contribution of resource allocation across districts to overall regional efficiency. According to the results, Termez district (3.967) and Denov district (2.718) have relatively high values. Based on the nature of this coefficient, these areas combine a substantial economic share with a high level of efficiency. Meanwhile, the lowest values are observed in Oltinsoy (0.431) , Qiziriq (0.566) , and Qumqo'rg'on (0.609) , indicating that both efficiency and economic share are relatively limited in these districts.

Social Quality Index of Growth. First, the per capita gross regional product of each district was divided by

the corresponding regional-level indicator. The obtained value was then multiplied by the average growth rate. This means that even if a district demonstrates high economic growth, if its per capita product remains below the regional average, the social contribution of such growth to public welfare is relatively limited.

According to the analysis, Termez district records the highest value for this indicator as well, indicating that economic growth has increased proportionally with the per capita gross regional product of the urban population. Relatively lower values are observed in Oltinsoy ((0.0529)) and Qumqo'rg'on ((0.0526)), where the impact of economic growth on public welfare remains limited.

Growth Sustainability Coefficient. At the initial stage, the variance of economic growth across districts was calculated. All results were then normalized within the range from 0 to 1. Since high variance usually reflects instability in economic growth, the normalized values were subtracted from 1 to obtain a more interpretable sustainability coefficient.

Muzrabot district demonstrates the highest level of growth stability. In addition, the values recorded for Denov and Jarqo'rg'on districts, as well as Termez district, also indicate a relatively sustainable growth pattern. By contrast, higher variance is observed in Sariosiyo, Qiziriq, and Oltinsoy districts, suggesting the need to improve the stability of economic growth in these areas.

Level of Economic Growth Diversification. The calculation was carried out based on the production shares of agriculture, industry, construction, and services across the districts. The results indicate that the level of diversification is relatively similar across all districts, suggesting that local economies are not strongly dependent on a single sector.

Integrated Indicator. All previously calculated indicators were normalized using the Min–Max normalization method. The general results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4
Integrated Indicator Values

Regions	Termez district	Oltinsoy	Angor	Boysun	Muzrabot	Denov	Jarkurgan	Kumkurgan	Qiziriq	Sariosiyo	Termez	Uzun	Sherobod	Shurchi
	0,752	0,449	0,432	0,722	0,423	0,609	0,251	0,066	0,152	0,181	0,366	0,379	0,589	0,331

According to the results presented in Table 4, no benchmark or ideal district was identified. The leading areas are Termez district ((0.752)), Boysun district ((0.722)), and Denov district ((0.609)). Relatively stable regional performance was recorded in Oltinsoy, Angor, Muzrabot, and Sherobod districts.

At the same time, Jarqo'rg'on, Qumqo'rg'on, Qiziriq, Sariosiyo, Termiz, Uzun, and Sho'rchi districts demonstrate considerable potential for improving the quality of economic growth. In these areas, priority should be given to strengthening technological efficiency, increasing labor productivity, and improving the effective use of available resources.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, it should be noted that economic growth in the districts of the region is predominantly driven by capital accumulation and labor resources. A relatively high ratio of technological progress to overall economic growth was identified only in Termez district and Boysun district. In the remaining districts, most of the analyzed indicators show that economic growth is mainly extensive in nature.

The results of the integrated indicator also reveal notable differences among the districts. Termez district, Boysun district, and Denov district demonstrated stronger growth performance in terms of both qualitative and quantitative indicators. Other districts, meanwhile, have significant potential to improve the quality of economic growth by increasing technological efficiency, strengthening labor productivity, and ensuring more effective use of available resources.

Overall, the findings indicate that simply increasing the volume of gross output is not sufficient to ensure sustainable regional economic growth. Therefore, one of the key directions of structural reforms should be the enhancement of labor productivity in areas with abundant labor resources. This, in turn, will contribute to improving the quality, stability, and long-term sustainability of regional economic growth.

REFERENCES

1. Achelashvili, M., & Achelashvili, K. Regional management of economic growth // *The Caucasus & Globalization*. – 2007. – No. 5.
2. Mohammad, A. N. M. B. Economic growth of Malaysia // *Politics, Economics and Innovation*. – 2020. – No. 3(32).
3. Babaev, B. D., & Dubrovsky, S. P. Economic growth: An expanded interpretation. Quality of economic growth // *Ekonomika obrazovaniya*. – 2015. – No. 1.
4. Gelin, M. V. Quantity and quality of economic growth // *Izvestiya SPbGEU*. – 2007. – No. 2.
5. Deryagulyeva, O., Bekniyazova, L., Geldimyradova, A., & Gurbanov, A. Theories of economic growth // *IN SITU*. – 2023. – No. 2.
6. Krivoruchko, M. Yu. Analysis of the dynamics of gross regional product based on the methodology of neoclassical growth theory // *BI*. – 2015. – No. 2.
7. Mamatov, M. A. Quality of economic growth // *Ekonomika i finansy (Uzbekistan)*. – 2016. – No. 3.
8. Teplov, M. N. On the issue of assessing the quality of regional economic growth // *Problemy razvitiya territorii*. – 2010. – No. 5.
9. Shkiperova, G. T. Assessing the quality of economic growth in the North-West regions: Ecological aspect // *Natsionalnye interesy: priority i bezopasnost*. – 2012. – No. 22.

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